

Mobilise-D Scoping Review: Abstract Screening Worksheet

Overview:

- This review will explore the potential of DMOs as clinical trial endpoint measures by identifying, existing evidence on their construct validity, prognostic value, and responsiveness to intervention
- Our four research questions aim to explore the following:
 - RQ1: The differences in GaWPs between target populations and healthy controls
 - RQ2: The relationship between GaWPs and traditional clinical measurements
 - RQ3: The prognostic value of GaWPs
 - RQ4: The use of GaWPs as endpoints in interventional studies

Question 1: Should this paper be included in full-text review? (YES or NO)

Questions to ask yourself:		YES or Unsure	NO
A	Is the study on an included population ? <i>(human studies on Parkinson's, Multiple Sclerosis, COPD, hip fracture)</i>	Proceed	Discard
B	Does the study assess gait speed, gait analysis or an included GaWP ? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - See reference sheet for list of included GaWPs - Note that some clinical walking tests are included as measures of gait speed (4 meter walk, 10 meter walk, timed 25 foot walk, etc.) and others are not. See reference sheet for details 	Proceed	Discard
C	Is the study an included design ? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Included Designs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Observational ▪ Case-control (comparing diseased group vs. healthy group) ▪ Cohort ▪ Cross-sectional ▪ Longitudinal ▪ Interventional o Excluded Designs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Case study ▪ Case series (Series of case studies published together) ▪ Review paper 	Proceed	Discard
D	Could the study address one of our research questions ? <i>(answer YES if any of the following apply)</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RQ1: Could the study explore the <i>differences in DMOs/GaWPs between healthy controls and a target population</i>? - RQ2/RQ3: Could the study <i>explore a relationship between DMOs/GaWPs and included measurements (RQ2) or outcomes (RQ3) in a target population</i>? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Relationships could be in the form of a correlation, empirical relationship, odds ratio, risk ratio, hazard ratio, prediction model, multivariate analysis, or other association measure - RQ4: Does the study appear to be an <i>interventional study in a target population with a DMO/GaWP as an endpoint</i>? 	Proceed	Discard
E	Are at least 5 individuals (or 20 events for RQ3) included in the final analysis?	Proceed	Discard
		YES	NO
F	Are there any other inclusion criteria that the study clearly does not meet ?	Discard	Keep

***If you are unsure, please be conservative and include the study in full-text review.*